

FORMING METRICS OF INDICATORS FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF SOCIAL MARKETING SYSTEM OF ENTERPRISES ON THE INTERNATIONAL MARKET

T. Androsova, O. Kot, V. Kozub, L. Chernyshova

The key directions created in theoretical and empirical researches of marketing effectiveness are systematized. The essence, functions, tasks and order of forming metrics of indicators for the assessment of social marketing system at the enterprises are given. The main directions of evaluating efficiency of the enterprises activity connected with the assessment of the efficiency of marketing activity at the enterprises are characterized and their shortcomings are defined. The expediency of the formulation of the indicator estimating efficiency of socialization taking into account marketing concepts, which influence the enterprise as a subject is proved. The metrics of indicators for the assessment of a social marketing system at the enterprises in the international market is created and characterized.

Keywords: system, social marketing, international market, metrics of indicators, effect.

ФОРМУВАННЯ МЕТРИКИ ПОКАЗНИКІВ ОЦІНКИ СИСТЕМИ СОЦІАЛЬНОГО МАРКЕТИНГУ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ НА МІЖНАРОДНОМУ РИНКУ

Т.В. Андросова, О.В. Кот, В.О. Козуб, Л.О. Чернишова

Систематизовано ключові напрями, що сформувалися в теоретичних і емпіричних дослідженнях маркетингової результативності. Виділено проблеми розробки показників оцінки та діагностики системи соціального маркетингу, що пов'язані з розробкою показників оцінки ефективності бізнесу. З'ясовано завдання, які вирішує побудова системи показників оцінки соціального маркетингу підприємств на міжнародному ринку. Охарактеризовано етапи аналізу маркетингових витрат при виході на міжнародний ринок. Наведено сутність, функції, основні завдання та порядок формування метрики показників оцінки системи соціального маркетингу підприємств. Визначено сукупність притучень про характер досліджуваних взаємодій у маркетинговій системі. Як базові метрики системи маркетингу обрано маркетингові витрати. Визначено перелік витрат (видатків) на маркетингову діяльність, що формують її собівартість. Охарактеризовано основні напрями оцінки ефективності діяльності підприємств, що пов'язані з оцінюванням ефективності маркетингової діяльності підприємств, та

визначено їх недоліки. Доведено доцільність формулювання показника, що оцінює ефективність соціалізації з урахуванням маркетингових концепцій, до впливу яких схильне підприємство – параметр стабільної повторюваності ефекту R_E , який показує відношення маркетингових витрат до загальних виробничих витрат підприємства. Розмежовано властивості системи маркетингу, агреговані у властивості стабільної повторюваності ефекту. Сформовано та охарактеризовано метрику показників оцінки системи соціального маркетингу підприємств на міжнародному ринку.

Ключові слова: система, соціальний маркетинг, міжнародний ринок, метрика показників, ефект.

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ МЕТРИКИ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ОЦЕНКИ СИСТЕМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНОГО МАРКЕТИНГА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ НА МЕЖДУНАРОДНОМ РЫНКЕ

Т.В. Андросова, Е.В. Кот, В.А. Козуб, Л.А. Чернышова

Систематизированы ключевые направления, сформировавшиеся в теоретических и эмпирических исследованиях маркетинговой результативности. Приведены сущность, функции, задачи и порядок формирования метрики показателей оценки системы социального маркетинга предприятий. Охарактеризованы основные направления оценки эффективности деятельности предприятий, связанные с оценкой эффективности маркетинговой деятельности предприятий, и определены их недостатки. Доказана целесообразность формулировки показателя, оценивающего эффективность социализации с учетом маркетинговых концепций, влиянию которых подвержено предприятие. Сформирована и охарактеризована метрика показателей оценки системы социального маркетинга предприятий на международном рынке.

Ключевые слова: система, социальный маркетинг, международный рынок, метрика показателей, эффект.

Statement of the problem. Dynamic changes of the last years in economy of our country revealed a number of new relevant tasks, which have theoretical character and have great scientific and practical value for ensuring sustainable and dynamic development of enterprise structures. Formation and assessment of effectively functioning system of social marketing at the enterprises of the commercial sector in the course of entry into the international markets are one of such tasks.

To mark out the importance of social marketing means to establish its contribution to the final results of the concrete enterprise activity, without being guided by general economic indicators. Quantitative technique of evaluating efficiency of marketing demands studying the contribution of expenses on marketing and all other expenses for receiving

profits, but not the calculation relating advertising expenses to sales volume. Important determination of the effect gained from implementation of marketing activity, and establishment of system stability of the enterprise on the basis of the received indicators expressing the marketing concept adopted by the enterprise and, as a result, efficiency of marketing actions. Therefore, there is a problem of marketing expenses optimization to the west concerning the increase in social responsibility of the enterprises, which are to be solved within the introduction and assessment of a system of social marketing at the enterprises.

Review of the latest research and publications. Problems of measurement and assessment of social marketing results for a long time take central place in the works of domestic and foreign researchers. Representatives of foreign science schools among which are R. Blom, F. Kotler, R. Morgan, A. Teta, D. Nort, G. Assel, D. Aaker, G. Haken, G. Baghiev, A. Shulga, O. Firsanova, N. Moiseyeva and others, made an essential contribution to the theory and methodology of management of social responsibility. Separate theoretical and methodological aspects of use and assessment of social marketing system is a subject of scientific discussions among such domestic scientists as: D. Akimov, I. Bulls, T. Dubovik, T. Stahl, V. Zhivetin, V. Samokhvalov, M. Chernov, I. Feraponova, L. Balabanova, N. Moiseyev, M. Konishev, etc. Today the majority of publications are devoted to the questions of the assessment of marketing operations efficiency or its separate functions with the methods of the marketing audit. In theoretical and empirical researches of marketing effectiveness, it is possible to allocate several key directions, which created [1]:

- development of theoretical background for the assessment of the effectiveness of the organization within the theory of the enterprise, the theory of market value of the enterprise, the theory of organizational behavior;
- allocation of marketing drivers of growth of profitability at the enterprise;
- discussions concerning the maintenance of a concept of marketing assets as a factor for the value of the enterprise;
- a search of effective distribution of efforts in a marketing complex (commodity policy, pricing, distribution and communications);
- formation of new approaches to the assessment of marketing effectiveness within the theory of marketing of the partnership.

The specified approaches allow to measure a set of different indicators belonging to marketing. However, the ways to the assessment of economic and social effects gained at the implementation of programs for the socialization of commercial activity remain insufficiently developed.

The objective of the research is the development of recommendations concerning the formation of metrics of indicators for the assessment of a social marketing system of the enterprises in the international market.

Presentation of the research material. Development of indicators for the assessment and diagnostics of a social marketing system is the task connected with the solution of the following problems of the development of indicators for the assessment of business efficiency:

- lack of direct link of indicators by means of which the efficiency of marketing functions is estimated, with financial results of the companies;
- commitment of the indicators existing at that time to functional processes when it is necessary to display structural and functional unity of a business system;
- the inability of the indicators calculated from the positions of short-term consideration to characterize system stability of the company in the future due to long-term effects of an increase in value due to the involvement of new clients and marketing investments stimulating this gain;
- weak readiness of tools for measuring efficiency of the strategic investments connected with a phenomenon of a brand that produces imperceptible investigations that difficult give in to account;
- need for taking note of marketing decisions on the level of the invested capital innovation;
- disintegrating strategic and tactical levels (operational) functioning;
- inconsistency of the available multiple indicators of assessment which complicates business management.

The described above problem of economic measurements of the marketing system behavior gives an idea of the existing difficulties in the sphere of marketing systems metrology. Besides, general scientific requirements of uniqueness, adequacy and accuracy of measurements put forward the task of designing numerical q-measuring instruments of interpreting the received ratios to increase efficiency of the administrative function.

Thus, unlike traditional methods that have a number of noted shortcomings, the offered approach is intended to untie such tasks:

- separation of marketing actions effect from other actions of the company and assessment of the efficiency of all four elements of marketing mix;
- the ratio of marketing activity with the achievement of long-term results by means of asymptotic approach of the marketing ratio and total costs in the most effective state;
- justification of investments into marketing through the choice of an optimum ratio of the marketing and total costs depending on the nature of the industry.

The analysis of marketing expenses at entry into the international market is offered to be carried out in three stages:

1) studying of accounting reports and identification of cumulative profits of the enterprise in the ratio with two grouped items of expenditure (the marketing and total costs); classification of expenses according to the performed marketing functions (product, price, placement and promotion);

2) drawing up the table of expenses which includes the current items of expenditure, their grouping on the purposes of expenses on a concrete type of marketing activity; if necessary – further grouping of functional expenses of marketing on separate goods, marketing territories and market segments, to sales channels, consumers;

3) the search for optimum combinations of items of expenditure according to their functional influence on the formation of cumulative profits of the enterprise.

Transition to the analysis of functional dependences allows resolving an issue, essential to objective assessment, of a set of the major indicators and their sufficiency in the course of the assessment of the marketing activity result. The received indicators show structural interrelation of different aspects of the firm activity and give the generalizing assessment to efficiency, without pressing in the specification of the live work efficiency, use of fixed assets, reverse and capital investments, efficiency of material resources, efficiency of the new equipment and materials.

A set of target indicators is called metrics. It allows to estimate a measure of the approach to the enterprise performance of its purposes and is the measuring instrument of marketing activity effectiveness. It shows a measure how the objectives and a key performance indicator of marketing are quickly achieved [3]. The marketing metrics are the list of actions (indicators, estimates) that characterize a measure of marketing purposes achievement by the company through consistent measurements that constantly repeat. In such an understanding, assessment of an integrated indicator of efficiency based on the analysis of the efficiency of realization of system property of stability of the received return completely meets the requirements to the maintenance of marketing metrics. The concept of social marketing metrics acts as administrative information and as the instrument of management of processes of growth of trust and an increase at the level of the perceived responsibility of the enterprise to the consumer.

The main functions of metrics are activity control, tool and methodical maintenance, management of marketing, the search of innovative technologies of marketing, coordination of expenses on internal marketing. Functions of metrics define their main tasks [4]: coordination of the process of marketing activity with tactical and strategic tasks of business (internal marketing, internal benchmarking); preventive support of business

structures necessary technologies of key factors achievement; improvement of the process of marketing activity (efficiency assessment, control, audit of the contribution of marketing activity to progress of the organization); development and formation of metrics allow to respect the principles of concreteness, measurability, reach, realness, simplicity, availability of information, comparability, ability to integrate, balance and innovation. All specified principles adhere during the estimation of efficiency from the positions of system approach that allows passing to the description of the structure of marketing metrics of the assessment of social orientation efficiency of the enterprise.

The marketing structure as a separate element of an economic system is characterized by the violation of symmetry, multiple elections and correlations in considerable scales. Violation of symmetry is followed by the emergence of new properties that allow stating an ordered state and possibilities of management in a system. In the most general form of the task of management regarding the condition of a marketing system, it is possible to formulate so: to find a set of actions on a marketing system that operate provide an extremum of target functionality of the effect of marketing activity.

A set of assumptions concerning the nature of the studied interactions in a marketing system can be built to the following:

- in a system one optimal solution can be absent;
- it is appropriate to speak about the existence of a huge number of effective solutions which deny classical formulation of the efficiency concept as one possible state;
- it is necessary to investigate a system nonlinear correlations and trends which demonstrate the recurrent process of stability in reconstruction processes;
- nonlinear and asymmetric situations are the main catalyst of the economic systems evolution;
- study of nonlinearity will help to explain and provide manifestation in the systems of threshold and synergy effects, which define the moments of key decisions adoption in the points when the system can be extremely sensitive to small administrative actions.

Marketing expenses that are allocated in the author's approach can be understood as a transaction, as according to D. Nortom, the difference between the total and production (transformational) costs are transaction expenses [4]. Therefore, it is possible to assume that the complication of a market system that we observe leads to monotonous growth of marketing expenses connected with the provision and functioning of the market.

As basic metrics of a system of marketing expenses are chosen, belong to expenses on marketing activity, which form the cost of marketing activity:

- expenses on search (benchmarking), preparation and development of new technologies;
- the operating costs connected with planning, organization and management of marketing activity; expenses on preparation and retraining of personnel (increase in creativity of marketing activity);
- expenses on actions for the improvement of quality and level of products' competitiveness;
- expenses from ensuring the transaction efficiency (negotiations, contracts and so forth).

Respectively, the directions of economic effect should be connected with the improvement of the use of human, material, information resources, fixed assets, capital investments, with the improvement of a control system quality, with effect in the sphere of operation and usage of goods.

Now there are several directions of assessing efficiency of the companies' operation. In the course of economic thinking evolution, consecutive transition from an economic (market) to cost mentality was carried out, and within both concepts, economic indicators of result supplement each other. At economic thinking into the forefront, management of internal expenses acts for the increase in indicators of profitability [5, p. 145].

The influence of decisions made are considered minimum at the moment. Such an approach emphasizes the ideas of marginal analysis in which the criterion of efficiency is equality of limit expenses and profits. Cost approach assumes that it is impossible to estimate the efficiency of activity irrespective of the environment of the company [6]. In such treatment, the analysis of the enterprise efficiency is connected not only with profit indicators but with prospects and risks of receiving the arrived. In the cost approach, assessment of marketing activity efficiency is identified with the assessment of investment attractiveness. A number of scientists – V. Zhivetin, V. Samokhvalov, M. Chernov, I. Ferapontova – consider that the efficiency of marketing policy relative to the concrete enterprise (to the industry, industry groups) consists of results of improvement of production and marketing activity behind the following main directions: optimum use of potential of the market, including for a new product; increase in reliability of projections; finding of a segment of the market of these goods; increase inaccuracy of the analysis of balance of the market, etc. [7].

L. Balabanova suggests to estimate the efficiency of marketing in a section of buyers, marketing integration, adequacy of information, strategic orientation, operational efficiency [8].

N. Moiseyeva, M. Konisheva give indicators of marketing activity on functions (market research, assortment policy, marketing activity,

communication activity) and generalizing indicators (profitability, the activity of strategy). The marked-out authors approached the development of an algorithm of calculation of an estimated indicator of the efficiency of marketing more but did not develop a scale for the quality standard of marketing and model of calculation of an integrated indicator of efficiency [9, p. 94].

Most of the American practitioners claim that the effect of marketing activity consists of the growth of sales volumes and profit [10]. However, the end result except a marketing component is affected by other components of the capacity of the enterprise – management, organizational structure, production capacities, technology, financial stability, investments, the information potential, therefore, it is possible to consider that such assessment is too simplified.

G. Assel suggests to estimate the efficiency of marketing activity as the efficiency of expenses on marketing that allows by means of economic and statistical methods to investigate the dependence between expenses on marketing and result – the sales volume or profit [4].

The given approaches and methods of assessment of the efficiency of marketing activity have a number of shortcomings connected directly with problems of measuring marketing effectiveness. Therefore, there is a need for the formulation of an indicator that estimates the efficiency of socialization taking into account marketing concepts to which influence the enterprise is inclined. At the same time, it is expedient to study structural role of marketing expenses in the general budget of the enterprise, the analysis of which is avoided by most researchers.

One of the main reasons for refusal of assessing expenses on marketing activity and its results depending on the accepted by the enterprise of the concept of marketing deem, lack of necessary information in the conditions of uncertainty, the complexity of economic processes of the market. The lack of methodology, the theory and the technique of distribution of the cumulative effect of the enterprise among the functions and products that are available in its activity is another reason. Besides, there is a problem of insufficiency of the criteria of efficiency of activity constructed on traditional financial models, in particular, lack of accounting of intangible assets – that added value which they create. D. Aaker who developed the concept of the capital of a brand tried to fill the gap connected with a lack of the approach to the estimation of the cost of a brand focused on consumption. Suggests understanding a number of the assets and liabilities connected with a brand, its name and a symbol as the capital of the D. Aaker brand. All specified problems can be fixed in case of definition and forecasting of expenses on marketing activity taking into account the property of stable repeatability of the marketing system effect.

The method of definition and forecasting of expenses on marketing activity taking into account property of stable repeatability of marketing system influence is aimed at the analysis of both the current results / effects of activity of the company, and future, long-term effects which will be caused by the actions of last period and also allows to estimate impact of a brand (a contribution to the formation of profits). At the identification in the resultant function of income of the influence of the factors which are not connected with the total material costs in terms of money, the contribution of these factors can be estimated quantitatively and carried to influence of intangible assets on the formation of the enterprise profits.

Thus, all described effects have to find reflection in a resultant indicator of the marketing activity efficiency of the enterprise. In the conditions of formation of hierarchical structures of management of the system of marketing of definition of an optimum order of distribution of the budget for types of activity demands coordination of actions at this or that level of hierarchy of management taking into account a multiple-factor, probabilistic situation and characteristics of advantage of inter-level relationship which gradually change.

An opportunity to count efficiency not only within a single period but also to define and predict the potential of a marketing system in the long term answers a task of assessment of valency of a marketing system. Valency is a characteristic that expresses the potential force, a possibility of each element or the subject of a concrete system to interact with the system of other hierarchy or to replace it at the appropriate level of management.

For economic and social systems is especially relevant introductions (concerning assessment and the analysis of internal communications), model standard interaction [11]. Valency as a concept opens "the nature of communications of interaction" [12]. As a measure of valency, there can be accepted standards – stable repeatability of the effect of RE (repeatability effect) which shows the attitude of marketing expenses to the total production costs of the enterprise (the total costs minus autocorrelations, marketing for elimination, at the creation of function of income).

As an economic measure of valency, it is expedient to accept such size of marketing expenses that begins to make a contribution to the formation of profits on the implementation of interaction, carrying out the transaction. In this context valency is the instrument of classification of trajectories of development of the enterprise depending on the chosen marketing concept and shows the necessary and sufficient level of accounting of the properties of a system of marketing aggregated in property of stable repeatability of the effect that is given in table 1.

Table 1

The properties of a system of marketing aggregated in property of stable repeatability of effect

Properties	Manifestation forms
Flexibility	it is shown in property of stability because of ability of a system of marketing to change the structure with a certain speed with a sustainable development goal of both the system and a system which uses the function of marketing maintenance
Lag effect	it is shown in property of adaptability because of the ability of a marketing system to resist external and internal indignations and actions which can change it
Adaptation	it is shown in property of repeatability of actions through a possibility of a system to adapt to such changes as the movement and development
Reliability	it is shown in the property of stability of obtaining result because of the ability of a system to perform the put functions at certain restrictions and necessary profitability, that is with minimum flows
The property is a lot of criteria for selection of decisions	it is shown in property of repeatability through an opportunity in the conditions of the incompleteness of information to receive a zone of exactly economic decisions (an interval of the size of expenses on marketing activity), but not the unambiguous decision

Thus, such interpretation of metrics of assessing the system effectiveness of social marketing is based on the use of traditional indicators of the budget of trade enterprise (block 1 – is data processing of the budget), but on the basis of modern optimizing and static procedures readiness of a marketing system of the enterprise for the use of a system of social orientation (pic. 1) allows to estimate (block 2).

Additional metrics are elements of criteria block 3 – economic, social effect and others which taking into account characteristics of economic and social stability of the gained effect give the chance to allocate the parameter of stable repeatability of effect (RE) as a key criterion. Being guided by the value of this parameter it is possible to speak about the degree of readiness of the enterprise for use of instruments of social marketing and the formation of its system according to the offered principles and elements. The analysis of the RE parameter allows defining the optimality of the cost breakdown of the enterprise through different types of economic functions. RE is directed to the formation of a resistant structural ratio for the most effective reconstruction of system elements (components, subsystems) during the implementation of the continuous changes caused by the action

of the environment. It is allocated by us the RE parameter allows to characterize and calculate structural efficiency of marketing expenses at the preservation of the relations in the system.

Fig. 1. Formation of metrics of indicators for assessing social marketing system of the enterprises in the international market

Conclusion. On the basis of addition of the existing system of indicators of assessment of efficiency of marketing social programs the developed metrics of indicators of assessment of readiness of the enterprises for use of the concept of social marketing which forms a basis of adoption of strategic decisions concerning forecasting and planning of effectiveness

of use of a system of social marketing by the enterprises in the international market. At further stages of development of the offered approach, there is an opportunity to study the catastrophic states connected with an increase in the level of instability of a system and to make preventive decisions concerning the choice of the most effective trajectories of development from a huge number of available. Stated allows allocating elements of a marketing metrics of the concept of social marketing which deserve studying and creation of the mathematical model.

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Androsova Tatyana, Candidate of Sciences (comparable to the academic degree of Doctor of Philosophy, PhD), Professor, Department of International Economics, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Klochkivska str., 333, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: 0507784006.

Андросова Тетяна Василівна, канд. екон. наук, проф., кафедра міжнародної економіки, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: вул. Ключківська, 333, м. Харків, Україна, 61051. Тел.: 0507784006.

Андросова Татьяна Васильевна, канд. экон. наук, проф., кафедра международной экономики, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: ул. Ключковская, 333, г. Харьков, Украина, 61051. Тел.: 0507784006.

Kot Olena, Candidate of Sciences (comparable to the academic degree of Doctor of Philosophy, PhD), Associate Professor, Department of International Economics, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Klochkivska str., 333, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: 0508555484; e-mail: elvkot@gmail.com.

Кот Олена Володимирівна, канд. екон. наук, проф., кафедра міжнародної економіки, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: вул. Ключківська, 333, м. Харків, Україна, 61051. Тел.: 0508555484; e-mail: elvkot@gmail.com.

Кот Елена Владимировна, канд. экон. наук, доц., кафедра международной экономики, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: ул. Ключковская, 333, г. Харьков, Украина, 61051. Тел.: 0508555484; e-mail: elvkot@gmail.com.

Kozub Victoria, Candidate of Sciences (comparable to the academic degree of Doctor of Philosophy, PhD), Associate Professor, department of International Economics and Management of Foreign Economic Affairs, Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics. Address: Tankopiya str., 31/2, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61091. Tel.: 0677055426; e-mail: kozub.viktoria71@gmail.com.

Козуб Вікторія Олександрівна, канд. екон. наук, доц., кафедра міжнародної економіки та менеджменту ЗЕД, Харківський національний економічний університет ім. С. Кузнеця. Адреса: вул. Танкопія, 31/2, м. Харків, Україна, 61091. Тел.: 0677055426; e-mail: kozub.viktoria71@gmail.com.

Козуб Виктория Александровна, канд. экон. наук, доц., кафедра международной экономики менеджмента ВЭД, Харьковский национальный экономический университет им. С. Кузнеця. Адрес: ул. Танкопия, 31/2, г. Харьков, Украина, 61091. Тел.: 0677055426; e-mail: kozub.viktoria71@gmail.com.

Chernyshova Larisa, Candidate of Sciences (comparable to the academic degree of Doctor of Philosophy, PhD), Associate Professor, Department of International Economics, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Lenin pr., 101, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: 0974523011; e-mail: lach.2803@gmail.com.

Чернишова Лариса Олексіївна, канд. екон. наук, доц., кафедра міжнародної економіки, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: пр. Ілліча, 101, м. Харків, Україна, 61019. Тел.: 0974523011; e-mail: lach.2803@gmail.com.

Чернышова Лариса Алексеевна, канд. экон. наук, доц., кафедра международной экономики, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: пр. Ильича, 101, г. Харьков, Украина, 61019. Тел.: 0974523011; e-mail: lach.2803@gmail.com.

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